

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRAGMATIC IN TEXT DECODING

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Abstract: *The article discusses the issues of pragmatic and linguopoetic study of texts of fiction, the things that unite these approaches and the differences that exist between them. Especially interesting is the use of these two aspects of text study when applied to the text of verbal-fiction, where the dominant function is the influence function, and the message function, which is certainly present in the text, recedes into the background.*

Key words: *pragmatics, communication, meanings, context, addressee, speaker, intention, verbal and nonverbal intensions, presuppositions, pragmatic effect of the message, planned and unplanned, pragmatic setting, intertextuality, speech activity.*

Pragmatics plays an important role in the study of communication because it focuses its attention on the communicative part of an utterance in different communicative situations. The pragmatic approach in the description of language has influenced the development of linguistic research on the text as a tool of language communication. The text is understood in line with the ideas of the modern stage of the systematic approach and based on the principle of communicativeness and is considered in the communicative space.

Characterizing any text, it is necessary, on the one hand, to distinguish the pragmatics of words and sentences, and on the other hand - the pragmatics of the text, as it is created by combining all the pragmatic meanings of those language units and syntactic constructions, which are included in the text. Moreover, pragmatics is influenced by the factor of the connection of linguistic units and, accordingly, those pragmatic meanings that are included in their composition, their realization in the context and their relation to the presupposition. The concept of pragmatics cannot be referred only to the concept of pragmatic meanings of linguistic units. This concept is much broader and includes issues related to the participants' understanding of the communicative process of linguistic units and speech works, depending on the linguistic and non-linguistic experience of people, and therefore pragmatics studies such extralinguistic factors as subject, situation and participants in the language act [4].

In this case, it should be noted that it is through the pragmatics of the whole text that the interaction of linguistic factors with extralinguistic factors is formed. For the

study of text pragmatics, the components of text pragmatics are distinguished: pragmatics as an obligatory category of each text, which takes into account the presence of addressee and addressee, the attitude of the addressee to the addressee, the pragmatic setting of the text, pragmatic content and pragmatic effect [1].

Each component of the text has its own pragmatic significance. Obligatory pragmatic plan of each text takes into account the fact that the text is formed primarily as a unit of communication with a specific purpose. If there is no purpose, the text loses its communicative features.

It is impossible to imagine the pragmatics of the text without an addressee and an addressee. The addressee, as a text creator, has his own goals, tastes, preferences, which is embodied in the transmitted message. The addressee dictates the choice of vocabulary and text structure. The role of the addressee determines not only the socio-ethical side of the speech, it makes the speaker take care of its organization, that is, the processing of speech is also subjected to the addressee factor [3]. Another component of pragmatics deserves attention - the meaning of the addressee's attitude. Planning the solution of his communicative tasks, the addressee forms the text, which is realized in its division into certain parts, each of which is characterized by semantic fragments.

Creating the text, the addressee selects the sentences to realize his goal, but at the same time this choice is also determined by the addressee's intention - the expectation of certain information in the text. Intention is the intention of the sender of the message, the purpose of which is to influence the recipient of the message. It is to the sphere of mental activity we will refer the author's intention.

If we consider the text as a communicative unit, the main stages, which the author passes, creating a text, are: 1) determination of a life situation with certain problems that need to be solved with the help of certain methods; 2) intension, as the author's internal prompting and 3) selection of linguistic units to embody the author's communicative intent [5]. If the same process is considered in terms of verbal/nonverbal, then we can argue that the intention of the addressee consists of two stages, where at the first stage the non-verbal component is implemented, and at the other - the linguistic design of the addressee. Intention, in turn, is realized on three levels: the author's intention, composition and style of the work. At the level of intention the theme of the message is formed, at the level of composition - the choice of the order of the sequence of themes, at the level of style - the choice of linguistic forms, their combinations [1]. In general, intension can be seen as a type of desire, for the realization of which a person will apply certain actions. Intention can be divided into two types: initial and final. Initial intension is the speech action during which the addressee forces the addressee to give out certain information. Final intention is that goal, which is realized with the help of speech activity and which is actually the intention of the author.

The next stage in the formation of the text is the pragmatic setting, which is realized in the text already verbally with the help of linguistic means, which are filled with pragmatic elements. Moreover, these pragmatic elements are a system of linguistic units, which are located at all levels and are combined in one text with one purpose - to exercise influence on the addressee.

The pragmatic content of the text is the content that accentuates the conditions and purpose of conveying the meaning of the text. This content gives the right direction to the text, reveals the interaction between the addressee and the addressee and together with the semantic content is transmitted to the addressee. It is the pragmatic content that is associated with the pragmatic influence, the purpose of which is to implement the communicative settings of the addressee. In addition, in the pragmatic content is the main idea that guides the thoughts of the addressee and causes the planned reaction. Pragmatic content is directly related to the author's intention, which determines the choice of units and principles of the linguistic structure of the message. In this regard, we emphasize the importance of the addressee's understanding of the intent. The pragmatic content is largely influenced by the type of addressee, since understanding requires not only life experience, but also language experience. The addressee has no chance of pragmatic effect if the addressee does not understand the message sent. This is why the behavior of the partners in the situation must be determined in advance. What is in the future situation must be accessible to the perception of all partners [5]. Here it is appropriate to add the basic conditions of the correct interpretation of the text: completeness of the text, correctness of language and sufficiency of nonlinguistic factors, such as general knowledge of communicants about the situation [3].

To the last component of pragmatics we referred the pragmatic effect. The pragmatic effect is "the resultant of those forces of the text that correspond to its functional-purpose characteristics".

Very often pragmatic effect is understood as the adequacy or inadequacy of communication. Let us call such adequacy pragmatic and derive a pattern: pragmatic adequacy increases with increasing degree of perception of the text. Therefore, if we talk about the pragmatic value of the text as a whole, it depends primarily on the pragmatic effect or, in other words, on the impact of the text on the behavior and emotions of the addressee.

Since the addressee takes into account the addressee's presupposition, he, as the author, influences the text implicitly. The perception of the text depends on the addressee's knowledge and awareness of the reality that is displayed in the text and on his understanding of the presented means of the language of communication. In this regard, the pragmatic effect can only have the potential to influence. Obviously, in some cases, this influence may not be realized. Some researchers consider two types

of pragmatic effect: planned (potential) and unplanned (actual). If they coincide, such an effect qualifies as a positive effect. If in the process of communication there is an effect opposite to the planned one, they say about a negative effect. Here it becomes clear how important it is to take into account the following factors in order to achieve a positive pragmatic effect: the content of the statement, the nature of the signs that participate in this statement and the type of addressee.

The analyzed components of pragmatics do not act in isolation; they can represent a whole chain of interrelated components. The "trigger mechanism" for the interconnection of these components and for the formation of communication can be the addressee's intention. It is realized in the text and passes to the next stage - to the pragmatic setting of the text, on the basis of which the pragmatic content of the text is formed, which creates the pragmatic orientation of the text and helps to realize the pragmatic effect.

Through this analysis, we conclude that it is the pragmatic setting is the key point of the pragmatics of the text. So, at the heart of the pragmatics of the text is the process of generating communication. The type of communication changes depending on the sphere of communication. And the sphere of communication, in turn, affects the choice of text types - in oral or written form. The text, which exists in finished form (formed in written form), is transmitted to the addressee on the initiative of the addressee (e.g., artistic text) or on the initiative of both the addressee and the addressee (e.g., business letter). Such a text is a graphically and spatially organized structure and the perception of such a text is characterized by consistency and integrity. In other words, perceiving a written text, the addressee first perceives the external features of the text (the number of chapters, pages, paragraphs), and then its content is fixed in the mind of the addressee. Oral text, by contrast, does not exist in material form and is generated only at the time of the message. The text of the oral form, of course, can be repeated, but it will already be a slightly different text, because its components, such as the content of the text (words, sentences), the reaction of the addressee and even the communicative situation may be different.

The classical model of communication "addressee - text - addressee" also functions in written communication. It can be presented from a different angle: message of the addressee - reading - understanding (perception) by the addressee. At the first stage information encoding takes place. Then the text is transmitted to the addressee, who decodes this message at the third stage. As N.F. Alefirenko thinks, the text is "the result of interaction of coding and decoding, voicing and understanding of the message"[2]. Thus it is necessary to tell, that informative text depends on how much information of the addressee coincides with the received information at the addressee at decoding. Obviously, at the stage of reading the text, the addressee cannot directly influence the addressee's message in any way.

But already at the next stage "the effectiveness of speech activity is increased by the active participation of the recipient of information, his attempt to remake and creatively interpret the message. [2] .

The above gives clear ideas about the whole process of the generation of a written text: one must "construct a statement from the words of a given language according to the rules of its grammar, relate it to reality, committing communication (locution), provide speech with purposefulness (illocution) in accordance with the communicative intention of the speaker: cause certain consequences (perlocution) in the listener [2].

The sphere of communication also affects the components of the communicative process (addressee-text-addressee). For example, unidirectional action on the part of the addressee in the scientific sphere is realized with the condition that the text is a product of the addressee's speech and cognitive activity. Therefore, the classical scheme of communication changes into the scheme of communication in scientific activity: addressee-text, on the one hand, on the other hand, in the same scientific sphere, but under a different situation, the text can be considered as an object of a bidirectional process: addressee-text-addressee.

If we consider communication in the form of written texts, namely business letters and contracts, in the above-mentioned chain "addressee-text-addressee" the second element of the model is emphasized, namely the text. Usually all business texts are characterized by intertextuality, in other words, they have a standard structure. For example, in contracts, the text has a title and several sub-titles with clearly numbered paragraphs. Business letters also consist of certain regulated structural and compositional elements. And in such texts it is their beginning that is especially significant: "the beginning of the message is particularly important, where the pragmatic picture of the whole text is drawn from the first lines".

Here it should be noted that the influence of the addressee in the formation of an appellative text is not as significant as, for example, in the texts of fiction or even in the texts of scientific literature. The reason is that such texts clearly set the algorithm of action with an emphasis on a certain addressee, so the addressee and addressee components go into the background. However, in the texts of business documents, despite their characteristic features, there are certain linguistic variants, which just depend on the addressee. In this case, the addressee together with the text come to the forefront of communication. The importance of the addressee can be confirmed by the following reflection. In any text, including the text of a business document, it is possible to find the intension of the addressee and the addressee. In order to decipher the text, the addressee uses the same bases that the addressee used: linguistic and social environment, experience, knowledge, psychological state, etc. In this case there is a superimposition of the role of the addressee on the role of the addressee; in other words,

in order to understand, analyze, penetrate the text, we must assume the role of the addressee. It is not difficult to notice that the same process can take place with the addressee, who, given the addressee's presupposition, takes on the role of the addressee.

Thus, it should be noted that, despite the different conditions of the life situation, each element of the classical model in a written text (especially in the text of a business document) is relevant and affects the other elements of the communication model.

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